

Metachromasia and Circular Dichroism induced by ATP and ADP : Evidence in Favour of Bent Phosphate Chain

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ATP, ADP and AMP bind the dye pinacyanol chloride stoichiometrically. Broad and multiple banded metachromasia are induced by ATP and ADP, but not by AMP. Thus ATP and ADP are the smallest chromotropes to induce metachromasia in the dye. These two compounds also induce strong dichroism in pinacyanol resolvable into three biphasic components corresponding to the observed bands in the metachromatic spectra. This induction of CD in the dye has been interpreted from the bent conformation of the phosphate chain, and not directly from the chiral deoxyribose moiety.

Metachromasia means the spectral blue-shifts exhibited by some cationic dyes due to their aggregation through cooperative binding on anionic polymers, called chromotropes¹. A chromotrope need not be a macromolecule, and small molecules like inositol hexaphosphate², inositol hexasulphate³, suramin sodium⁴ also induce metachromasia. Czikkely *et al.*⁵ showed from electron gas model and extended dipole model that aggregations of dyes to trimer or tetramer are quiet adequate to give the observed blue-shift in metachromasia ; so to exhibit metachromasia the aggregation of the dye molecules need not be extended indefinitely. Earlier attempts to induce metachromasia in dyes by ATP were not successful^{3,6}. The fully charged ATP and ADP have 4 and 3 anionic sites respectively ; theoretically⁵ both of them are expected to induce metachromasia in suitable dyes provided dye-cations can occupy all the available anionic sites in an ordered way. In our recent preliminary report⁷ we mentioned that ATP induces weak metachromasia in the strongly aggregating dye 1,9-dimethylmethylene blue, though it fails to induce metachromasia in common dyes like acridine orange and methylene blue. This shows ATP to be a weak chromotrope. In the present report we have selected another strongly aggregating dye pinacyanol (PCYN) and raised pH of the experimental solutions to 8.0 in order to render ATP and ADP fully charged. To our satisfaction not only ATP, but also ADP induce metachromatic spectral changes in the dye. AMP, however, does not induce metachromasia, though it binds PCYN. We retook this problem not only to use these biologically important molecules as chromotropes but also with the speculation that dichroism could be induced in the bound dyes from the asymmetric ribose moiety of ATP, ADP and AMP. Such dichroic studies could be useful in speculating whether the bent triphosphate chain conformation, as inferred from X-ray crystallography of disodium ATP crystal, is also maintained in ATP in aqueous solution in the native environment.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 represents the metachromasia induced in PCYN by ATP, ADP, AMP and tetrasodium pyrophosphate. Spectrum (A) is of $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$ PCYN in water. The peaks at 600 and 547 nm are due to the monomeric and dimeric forms of the dye respectively. The higher intensity of the dimer band even at this low concentration reflects the strong

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$ PCYN in (A) water, and in the presence of (B) AMP, (C) ADP, (D) ATP and (E) pyrophosphate all at pH 8.0 and polyanion to dye molar ratio (P/D) of 9.3, 10.3, 10.9 and 10.0 respectively ; (B'), (C'), and (D') are as same as (B), (C) and (D) respectively but at pH 4.0.

aggregating tendency of this dye. The spectrum changes to (B) on adding AMP to a AMP/dye molar ratio (P/D) of 9.3. Obviously AMP fails to induce metachromatic band, only the absorbances of the two peaks are reduced ; ADP added to the dye at P/D=10.3 induces multiple banded metachromasia having peaks at 485, 550, 600 and 640

nm with drastic reduction of the absorbance of the dimer band of the dye itself (spectrum C). The shape of the metachromatic band induced by ATP (spectrum D) is similar to that induced by ADP. In this connection the work of Pal and Ghosh⁸ is to be recalled which shows that the shape of metachromatic spectra of PCYN depends on the nature of the polyanions. Those polyanions which bind PCYN at all anionic sites with 1 : 1 stoichiometry exhibit broad and multiple banded metachromasia, while polyanions binding this dye at every alternate anionic sites with 2 : 1 stoichiometry induce sharp and single banded metachromasia. The pHs of these solutions are maintained between 8.0 to 8.2 and variations of P/D from 3 to 25 do not have any pronounced effect in the shapes of the metachromatic spectra. However lowering of P/D below 1 progressively abolishes the metachromatic bands, more rapidly in case of ADP. It is to be pointed out that metachromasia induced by all polyanions is facilitated by a reasonable excess of the polyanions, though the compound responsible for metachromasia has 1 : 1 anionic site to dye ratio¹.

The spectra (C') and (D') in Fig. 1 are of PCYN at the same concentration in the presence of ADP and ATP at P/D \approx 10 but at lower pH (4). It is interesting to note that ATP induces metachromasia in PCYN even at the acidic pH, but ADP does not. The spectrum of the dye-AMP system at this pH is almost identical with that of the dye. This weakening of chromotropic ability of ATP and ADP at lower pH may be one of the reasons for earlier failures in induction of metachromasia by them, as commercial samples of ATP and ADP are usually available in the form of acid salts. Just for comparison the spectrum (E) of the dye in the presence of tetrasodium pyrophosphate at the optimum P/D=10.0 is included. It seems that though pyrophosphate induces broad and multiple banded metachromasia in the dye, its chromotropic character is rather weaker than ATP and ADP since the absorbances at the peaks are somewhat lower than those of spectra (C) and (D).

The question naturally arises whether PCYN can bind at all the available anionic sites of ATP, ADP and AMP, or whether steric effect hinders exhaustive dye-binding. To ascertain this PCYN was titrated conductometrically by ATP, ADP and AMP (curves not shown). The conductometric titrations of PCYN by ATP, ADP and AMP show definite breaks at titrant to dye molar ratios of 4.1, 3.2, 2.1 respectively. These figures are very close to the number of negative charges per molecule of ATP, ADP and AMP respectively, indicating that one dye cation is bound at each anionic site and hence without any steric hindrance. It is to be noted that AMP also binds PCYN stoichiometrically though the system does not exhibit metachromasia.

Adenine is achiral, but ATP exhibits CD in the absorption region of the base⁹. This is obviously

due to induction of asymmetry in the base from the chiral ribose moiety. Such an induction of asymmetry could be extended to the dyes bound at the phosphates, but would gradually be feeble with increasing distance from the ribose moiety. If the induction of asymmetry from ribose were the only operating mechanism, we would expect strongest dichroism to be exhibited by AMP-dye system. The bound dyes would also exhibit Cotton effect if the dye molecules were arranged with systematic twists in one sense. To choose between the two mechanisms we recorded the CD spectra of PCYN in the presence of AMP, ADP and ATP at various P/D ratios. To our surprise we found that ATP and ADP induce very strong CD in PCYN with $[\theta]$ values as high as 10^5 , while AMP does not at all. This indicates that the induction of chirality in the bound dyes does not originate from the ribose moiety directly, but due to the aggregation of the dye molecules with systematic twist¹⁰⁻¹². The CD spectra in the visible range of $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$ PCYN induced by ATP and ADP at various P/D ratios are presented in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. The set of CD spectra in Fig. 2 shows

Fig. 2. CD spectra of $2.00 \times 10^{-5} M$ PCYN induced by ATP at pH 8.0 and P/D of (A) 3.5, (B) 8.8 and (C) 26.3, and (D) at pH 4.0 and P/D of 8.1; $[\theta]$ values are based on dye concentration.

that the shapes of the spectra are not much dependent on the variations of P/D from 3 to 26. Also ATP induces CD in PCYN at the acidic pH, with peaks and troughs a bit red-shifted. The CD spectra induced by ADP (Fig. 3) have all the features of those induced by ATP, with some difference in the range 460–480 nm. Lowering of P/D to about 3 reduces the $[\theta]$ value in case of ADP, unlike ATP. At higher P/D however, the magnitude of induced dichroism is higher in case of ADP. In acidic pH, ADP induces CD in the dye with distinct bands but with $[\theta]$ values reduced by about 100-fold (spectrum

not shown). Thus CD spectra of PCYN induced by ATP and ADP at pH 4 can distinguish between them.

Fig. 3. CD spectra of 2.00×10^{-5} M PCYN induced by ADP at pH 8.0 and P/D of (A) 3.2, (B) 8.0, (C) 24.0, and (D) 32.0.

The CD spectra in any case show several peaks and troughs, reminiscent to several bands in the respective metachromatic spectra (Fig. 1). In order to correlate metachromatic spectra and CD, we made an attempt to resolve the observed CD spectra induced by ATP (spectrum B, Fig. 2) and ADP (spectrum C, Fig. 3). The resolution have been done a bit arbitrarily by assuming the principal peaks and troughs around 600 and 520 nm to be symmetric. The resolved spectra are shown in Fig. 4. The ATP induced resolved spectrum is seen to consist of three biphasic components (A, B, C) having cross-overs at 485, 560 and 660 nm, the component CD spectra can reasonably be linked with the observed bands of the metachromatic spectra around 485, 555 and 650 nm (spectrum D, Fig. 1). The resolution around 480 nm in the PCYN-ADP system is not smooth however. In the single-banded metachromatic spectra of PCYN induced by some polyanions, the observed shoulder at 640 nm (Fig. 1) is missing and the corresponding CD spectra also do not exhibit any peak or trough in this region¹². The shoulder around 640 nm is invariably present in the broad and multiple banded metachromatic spectra of the dye, and this shoulder at 640 nm is also reflected in the corresponding CD spectra^{12,13}. The exhibition of a sharp and more or less single metachromatic band of PCYN in aqueous solution at high concentration of dye, or induced by a polyanion at low dye concentration forming polyanion to dye compounds with 2:1 stoichiometry, reflects the ordered stacking of the dye^{8,12,14}. The broad and multiple banded metachromasia of the dye induced by polyanions like nucleic acids, polyacrylate, polyvinyl sulphate⁸ and also by ATP and ADP in the

present report forming 1:1 stoichiometric compounds with the dye, reflect rather chaotic dye aggregation due to overcrowd. The normal all-*trans* structure of the dye may be forced to assume some *cis-trans* isomerisation to avoid steric obstruction in the crowded aggregates. Ballard and Park¹⁵ also suggested that the geometry of cyanine dye molecules is distorted upon aggregation, and they can be pictured as partially wrapping each other. The extended all-*trans* configuration of a cyanine dye has λ_{\max} at longer wavelength relative to the bent mono-*cis* isomer¹⁶.

Fig. 4. Resolution of the CD spectrum (B) of Fig. 2 into three component spectra (A), (B) and (C); (A'), (B') and (C') are the resolved components of CD spectrum (C) of Fig. 3.

No doubt the asymmetry of ribose in ATP and ADP initiates the observed dichroism in the bound PCYN, but the observed high $[\theta]$ values as well as the failure of AMP to induce CD in PCYN, indicate that the chirality triggered by ribose is enhanced due to aggregation of dye molecules on ATP and ADP with systematic twist. This idea gets strong support from the crystallographic report on ATP¹⁷ which shows that the triphosphate chain in ATP is folded towards the purine base, in contrast to inorganic triphosphate when the chain is extended and symmetric about the central P atom^{18,19}. The folding of phosphate chain in ATP, and presumably in ADP also, arranges the negative sites as if on a segment of a helix thus facilitating a helical arrangement of the bound PCYN cations; thus PCYN aggregates on ATP and ADP (and not on AMP) become chiral, though the dye monomer is symmetric, and hence the observed dichroism. The biphasic nature of each component CD spectra (Fig. 4) indicates strong chromophore-chromophore interaction.

Thus induction of CD in the extrinsic chromophore PCYN by ATP and ADP (and not by AMP) supports the idea that phosphate chains in these nucleotides are bent and not linear. Heyn and

Bretz⁹ from the dichroic studies inferred that ATP molecules in aqueous solution at high concentrations of electrolytes (MgCl₂, NaCl) associate forming head-to-tail stacks with very slightly distorted superimposition of the putines; the added electrolytes help in masking the charge of phosphate. The cationic dyes bound at phosphate will more effectively mask the negative charge of phosphate, and hence the possibility of stacking of ATP-dye complexes can not be ruled out. However, such head-to-tail stacking is not expected to further affect the spectroscopic character of bound dye, since the dye aggregated on phosphate chain of one nucleotide molecule will be placed far apart from the dye aggregate formed on the phosphate chain of the nearest nucleotide. Also the vertical distance between successive nucleotides may be increased when complexed with dyes due to steric effect between dye aggregates formed on every alternate nucleotides placed head-to-head. The present report gives the first dichroic evidence for the bent conformation of ATP (and also of ADP), though other technics like immunochemical studies²⁰, localised orbital calculations²¹, pmr and spin lattice relaxation study²² etc. also indicated the same conformation of ATP.

This is the first report on the induction of strong metachromasia in a dye by small polyanions like ATP and ADP. ATP and ADP should be in the fully charged form to act like a chromotrope. These findings confirm the earlier reports that a chromotrope need not be a macromolecule to induce metachromasia. Induction of CD in PCYN in acidic pH by ATP distinguishes it from ADP which almost fails to induce dichroism. Though induction of dichroism is initiated by the ribose of ATP and ADP, the observed high $[\theta]$ values indicate aggregation of the bound dyes with twist in one sense, presumably triggered by the bent conformation of phosphate chain in ATP and also in ADP.

Experimental

ATP (adenosine-5'-triphosphate, disodium salt), ADP (adenosine-5'-diphosphate, dicyclohexyl ammonium salt) and AMP (adenosine-5'-monophosphate, sodium salt) (Sigma) and pinacyanol chloride (PCYN, 1-ethyl-2-[3-(1-ethyl-2(1*H*)-quinolyldine)-propenyl]quinolinium chloride) (Serva Fein Biochemica) were used as such.

Stock solutions were made fresh. All experiments were done at room temperature (26°). In preparing the experimental solutions, polyanions were pipetted to the diluted dye.

Absorption and CD spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-150-02 spectrophotometer and a Jasco-500-C spectropolarimeter using 1.0 cm cuvettes.

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